

Enhancing Learning with Block Programming in Educational Robots

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Abstract

The block programming language allows users to create programs using visual elements that represent different commands and that can be connected to form programming code. Usually, this type of programming language is employed by kids and teenagers because of their accessibility, interactive interface, and easiness to develop and understand programs. Blockly is a set of libraries that provides a variety of programming blocks, representing programming language instructions and it can be used to build block-based visual programming libraries. The Ereko Research Group, at University of Brasília, works with mobile robots applied in STEM and robotics education, and several hands-on workshops are held every year. It was noticed, during the workshops, that programming presented several difficulties for the students. Therefore, the main objective of this work is to develop a library of visual blocks for each robotic educational model at Ereko, to ease the robots programming, code development, as well as code understanding and comprehension from workshop participants. The library development methodology consists in stages of definition, requirements analysis, library design, implementation, testing and documentation. The results obtained during the test of system and software usability show that the software interface presents good appearance and the library elements are well structured, however it was mentioned by the software test participants some difficulties about a certain redundancy of the blocks as well as the non-editable areas. Despite that, it is believed that the proposed system would simplify teaching arduino and programming, as well as facilitate the learning.

Keywords: Active Learning; Block Programming; Education Models; Robotics.

1 Introduction

It is notorious that programming presents big difficulties for university students (Pereira et al., 2019; Lima et al., 2020; Araujo et al., 2021; Braz et al., 2021), mainly because it demands high cognitive capacity to understand problems and write codes necessary for their resolution (Freitas Júnior et al., 2020; Fonseca et al., 2019; Lima et al., 2020; Luxton-Reilly et al., 2018; Souza, 2018). Over the years, several methods have emerged, such as those proposed by Saleiro et al. (2013) and Iturrate et al. (2013), which target the application of robotics in the development of programming learning environments. In these projects, robotics acts as a context for formulating and verifying hypotheses. Initiatives with this purpose seek to use robotics and technology in the educational field to motivate students and simplify the learning process.

In this sense, visual programming languages (VPL) allow users to create programs using graphic elements, such as blocks or flow diagrams, that represent different commands and can be interconnected to form codes. Currently, this type of approach is widely adopted in teaching children and adolescents due to its intuitive and accessible interface, which facilitates the process of developing, understanding and learning programming (Souza, 2018; Heinen, 2015; Pasternak, 2009; Ribas et al., 2016). The use of visual programming languages (VPL) makes it possible to mitigate several difficulties associated with traditional programming languages, such as problems related to syntax and complex system configurations. In addition to simplifying these technical aspects, VPLs encourage greater interest and engagement in learning computational logic. Furthermore, this approach favours the development of essential skills, including logical reasoning, critical reflection and autonomy, through strategies based on problem solving (da Silva Marinho et al., 2017; Souza, 2018).

Blockly (Google, 2024a) is a set of libraries developed by Google with the purpose of promoting programming education. Additionally, by connecting its blocks, it is possible to translate into multiple programming languages, including JavaScript, Python, PHP, Lua and Dart. Also, Blockly offers a wide selection of blocks that represent programming language instructions, ranging from simple variable declarations to complex mathematical operations, which significantly expands its capabilities to meet diverse software development requirements.

The Ereko research group at the University of Brasilia is dedicated to the study of educational robotics models, covering modular robots, mobile robots with wheels, and other similar devices. During the university extension workshops, held annually by the group, it was noticed that participants experienced considerable difficulty in dealing with programming. Therefore, the main objective of this article is to develop specific block libraries for each educational robotic model created by the group. These libraries aim not only to ease the university students in the robot project, construction and assembly, but also to simplify the process of robot programming by middle school teachers during the workshops, since block language is more suitable for younger school students. The use of block language is particularly advantageous because it allows students to focus on logical and structural aspects of programming. This makes the learning process more engaging and less intimidating, which is crucial for less experienced students (da Silva Marinho et al., 2017; Souza, 2018; Ribas et al., 2016). Additionally, the article aims to present the translation into C language, used when programming Arduino like devices. The library development follows a systematic sequence of stages, from requirements definition and analysis to library design, identification of necessary blocks, implementation, testing and documentation.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the educational models that served as the basis for the development of libraries. In Section 3, the methodology adopted is explained, while in Section 4 the results of the tests carried out will be presented. The conclusion and future perspectives are addressed in Section 5.

2 Educational Models of Ereko

This section descriptively presents the robot models used for creating the first test libraries. In section 2.1, an Anthropomorphic Robot is presented, while in section 2.2 a Wheeled Robot is described.

2.1 Ereko Anthropomorphic Robot

The Anthropomorphic robot developed by Ereko is a simple device designed specifically to address fundamental principles in robotics education. It is used in the extension hands on workshops with the purpose of introducing basic concepts, such as elementary programming with Arduino, assembling circuits using breadboards, as well as to introduce 3D modelling and printing, a technique used in the production of its parts.

This robot is made up of two main parts: the body and the head. The body acts as a support structure for a servo motor, to which the head is directly attached on its axis. The head, in turn, contains two LEDs, representing the eyes, and a buzzer taking the place of the mouth. Therefore, during the workshops, participants practice controlling the head rotation angle using the servo motor, activating the LEDs to emit flashes and generating buzzer sounds using a button or automatically, depending on the approach.

Although this robot is widely used in Ereko Group workshops for robotics beginners, it is common for participants to face challenges in both assembling the circuits and programming the device.

2.2 Ereko Wheeled Robot

The Wheeled Robot developed by Ereko is a mobile robot with differential drive, designed to introduce medium and high complexity concepts to beginners in the field of robotics, as opposed to the Anthropomorphic robot previously described in section 2.1.

The main structure of the robot is made up of a chassis that supports the essential components for its operation, such as Arduino, breadboard, H bridge, batteries, DC motors and wheels. All parts are manufactured using 3D printing, and workshop participants receive instruction in using the necessary tools to reproduce, modify and improve existing robot parts. Furthermore, they can model additional parts according to the specific demands of the project. The robot includes a Bluetooth module that communicates with a smartphone and transmits information to the Arduino via the serial port.

Due to its versatile nature, the wheeled robot allows the integration of other components to explore more advanced concepts. It is feasible to easily integrate ultrasonic sensors in strategic positions on the front and back of the robot, allowing participants to investigate data acquisition and plan, in programming, the robot's response when detecting an obstacle in front of it. A particularly interesting addition is a trailer equipped with a robotic arm and gripper, which can pose a motivating challenge for workshop participants, where they need to not only program the arm, but also control the robot's movement as it tows the trailer.

2.3 Workshops

The robots described above are used in workshops aimed at the students and teachers of secondary education in public schools. These training workshops are held only for teachers, and they cover both robots as well as pedagogical methodologies necessary for their use. This training workshop prepares teachers to replicate the sessions with their students and the covered contents can be easily adjusted, allowing a more effective adaptation to the specific needs of the school where they work.

The workshops are divided in two modules of four workshops each: the first one is based in the first robot model (the Anthropomorphic Robot) and covers the fundamental concepts of 3D modelling and printing, programming logic, assembly of basic circuits on protoboard and Arduino. The second one is based in the second robot model (the Wheeled Robot) and it focuses on more advanced concepts such as the use of sensors, DC motors, H-bridge and Bluetooth communication, in addition to creating applications on the Applinventor platform (MIT, 2024).

3 Methodology

This section presents the sequence of steps used in creating the block system for programming the robots. The first section presents the block library was created and the second section describes the interface where these blocks are used in programming.

3.1 Block Library

Blockly, developed by Google (2024a), consists of a set of libraries for visual programming. In order to encourage programming learning, this library is accompanied by a customization editor, designed to introduce programming concepts by connecting blocks, generating clean code in the chosen programming language, as well as enabling the editing and customization of this code. Widely adopted by children and teenagers, this library encourages them to create their own animations and interactive games.

Blockly offers a variety of blocks that represent instructions found in various programming languages, ranging from variable declarations to mathematical, logical and relational operations, as well as conditional and repetition structures, among other features. By interconnecting these blocks, the environment is capable of

automatically converting to languages such as JavaScript, Python, PHP, Lua and Dart. Therefore, Blockly has the following advantages:

- Open Source: Available with an open-source license in its own repository on GitHub;
- Extensible: Capable of satisfying all user demands;
- Code export: Offers the ability to convert blocks into conventional programming languages;
- Versatile: In addition to being an educational tool, it also supports multiple languages, along with a wide variety of functionalities; and
- Multilingual: Available in translation into more than 40 languages.

To create the libraries, the Blockly Factory tool (Google, 2024b) (Figure 1) was used, a development platform that enables users to design and customize blocks of code according to their individual needs. It works as an authoring tool, simplifying the generation of custom programming languages or the expansion of existing ones. Within this context, users have the possibility of specifying the available blocks, their functionalities and interconnection methods to form programs, such as selecting colours, formats, behaviours, returns, options, text fields, among other aspects. This simplified approach to programming replaces manually writing code with a drag-and-drop interface, making the coding process more accessible and intuitive, especially for those just starting out.

For these reasons, it was considered feasible to create specific libraries for each educational model used by the Ereko research group, not relying exclusively on Blockly brings advantages, such as the ability to customize blocks, more optimized performance, full control over the code to be created, flexibility to deal with specific group situations, efficient maintenance and integration with other tools. This makes it possible to adjust the code according to students' needs, ensuring effectiveness and continuous progress.

3.2 Interface Creation

Using JavaScript, HTML and CSS programming languages, a test interface was developed (Figure 1) with the purpose of allowing the visualization of the implemented libraries, as well as demonstrating the conversion of blocks to the C programming language. Furthermore, the user is offered the option of downloading the resulting code with the ".ino" extension, compatible with Arduino integrated development environments (IDEs), simplifying the process of compiling and executing the program, even for those who do not have prior knowledge of C programming language.

Figure 1. Test Version Interface

4 Results

Currently, two libraries have been developed, one for each educational robot described in section 2. Tests were carried out with the students and teachers, as well as members of the Ereko group. The tests were related both to the system functioning and to the software usability, with the purpose of collecting suggestions for improvement and feedback.

4.1 General Library

For general purposes, a category called "Include" (Figure 2) has been established for libraries to be added during programming. Additionally, there is the "Functions" category, which contains the main code functions to be transferred to the Arduino, such as the "void setup" and "void loop" functions (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Include Library

Figure 3. Function Library

4.2 Results of Ereko Anthropomorphic Robot

For the Anthropomorphic Robot, a specific library was developed, divided into sections related to its assembly during the workshops held, aiming to make it easier for participating teachers and students. These sections include:

- Eyes (Figure 4): blocks related to the LEDs in the robot's eyes;
- Mouth: Includes the blocks related to the buzzer;
- Head: Contains the blocks related to the motor that moves the head; and
- General: Incorporates function blocks that can be used in both the "void setup" and the "void loop".

Figure 4. Ereko Anthropomorphic Robot – Eyes Library example

Through the developed interface and library, tests were conducted and improvements were implemented over time (Figure 5). During the assembly process, C code is automatically generated alongside for the user. When

finished, the user can use the download button to generate the file with the ".ino" extension, compatible with the Arduino IDE. This way, the code can be compiled and executed easily.

Figure 5. Test example for Ereko Anthropomorphic Robot

4.3 Results of Ereko Wheeled Robot

For the Anthropomorphic Robot, a comprehensive library was developed, providing greater flexibility in editing blocks for the user. Thus, the following categories are presented:

- Serial (Figure 6): This category is related to asynchronous communication between an Arduino board and a computer or other device;
- Functions: This category encompasses blocks associated with pin configuration, digital values, component intensity control, conversion of value ranges and conditional structures; and
- Variables: This category includes blocks for declaring variables, such as bytes or integers (int). Furthermore, it has an assignment block, allowing variables already declared to be later used to receive results from operations.

Figure 6. Ereko Wheeled Robot – Serial Library example

In the same way as for the anthropomorphic robot, tests were conducted and improvements were implemented over time, using the interface and library developed. During the assembly process, C code is automatically generated alongside for the user. When finished, the user can use the download button to generate the file with the ".ino" extension, compatible with the Arduino IDE, thus facilitating the compilation and execution of the code.

4.4 System functioning and software usability

In order to check the integrity of the software, tests of system and software usability were done. In order to help the test participants, initial explanations about the software were made, such as what is the system objective and how is it works. After that, the participant should do the test using a code example from both robot models presented in section 2. Following, they should answer a form, providing feedback and improvement suggestions.

In the form, questions about experience of the users were made, for example, if it was the first contact with Arduino and block programming. In addition, questions related to the interface and the library functionalities, general blocks and layout are also present in the form. Furthermore, questions about how much efficiency the software could be in the teaching of arduino and programming concepts.

In total, 9 feedback answers were collected, of which only 2 people used Arduino for the first time and 1 used block programming for the first time. In general, the layout was considered very pleasant and received improvement suggestions like the ability to change the colours, the possibility to increase or decrease each area and the possibility to edit the code C area. In relation to the block elements, they also had a very good reception, however there was some balanced between the good and bad ratings about how intuitive the blocks are. Also, suggestions for improving blocks functionality descriptions, abstraction of details and code structure in C were proposed.

The first library, related to the Anthropomorphic robot, had very good ratings and 8 people think it is possible to learn programming in the proposed way. However, with respect to the structure within the library there was a balance of opinions. In addition, the need of reducing block redundancy, the creation of blocks with more advanced functions and the separation of functions before code were suggested. For the second library, using the Wheeled robot, the users also rated it as having pleasant appearance and 8 people think it is possible to learn programming in the proposed way. Moreover, again, the structure within the library showed some balance of opinions, and suggestions were made regarding the need of improving the general robot movimentation blocks, of improving the form of blocks connection and their respective codes, as well as adding more blocks.

Regarding the use of the system to teach programming, 66,7% says that they would use it and 77,8% believe that the software facilitates teaching arduino. In addition, 88,9% believe that the application is effective in teaching programming concepts. These data suggest that the software can not only make learning more accessible and engaging but, also it can be effective in conveying complex concepts in an intuitive and practical way. Some users have reported difficulties with locating certain blocks, the non-editing feature in the code area and the fact that some blocks already contain variable names. Despite this, one of the final comments highlighted that, compared to the Tinkercad platform (Tinkercad, 2024), used for design and 3D modelling, the proposed system is much more intuitive for users.

5 Conclusion and Future Perspectives

In the present study, the use of block programming for educational models was described with the objective of creating exclusive libraries for the robotic models developed by the Ereko research group at the University of Brasilia. This process was conducted systematically, aiming to guarantee efficiency, flexibility and integration of the developed blocks. Using the Blockly tool to create the new system, the results obtained in the test of system and software usability demonstrate that the blocks developed for the Anthropomorphic Robot and Wheeled Robot models were very good pleasant about appearance but had a balance opinion about the separation of blocks in the library. Additionally, also had difficulties with locating certain blocks of some blocks,

a non-edit code area, some blocks already contain variable names and redundancy blocks. Besides that, most participants would use the application and believe that it would facilitate the teaching of arduino, in addition to believing that it is effective in teaching programming concepts.

For future work, it is planned to incorporate the improvement suggestions provided by the group, which include reducing the redundancy of blocks, improving their code, enabling editing in the C code area, improving the colour palette of the libraries and evaluate and improve the system structure, as well as adding explanations about the functionalities of the blocks. Furthermore, we intend to expand the work to other educational models developed by the group.

6 References

- Araujo, A., Zordan Filho, D. L., de Oliveira, E. H. T., de Carvalho, L. S. G., Pereira, F. D., & de Oliveira, D. B. F. (2021, April). Mapeamento e análise empírica de misconceptions comuns em avaliações de introdução à programação. In *Anais do Simpósio Brasileiro de Educação em Computação* (pp. 123-131). SBC.
- Autodesk. "Tinkercad". Available in www.tinkercad.com/ (June 2024)
- Braz, A. C. R., Carvalho, L. S., Oliveira, E. H., Oliveira, D. B., Bittencourt, R. A., Santana, B. L., & Pereira, F. D. (2021, November). Tradução e validação de um inventário de conceitos sobre programação introdutória. In *Anais do XXXII Simpósio Brasileiro de Informática na Educação* (pp. 1253-1264). SBC.
- da Silva Marinho, A. R., Souza, G., Rosa, J., & de Moraes, P. S. (2017, October). O uso do Scratch na educação básica: um relato de experiência vivenciada no PIBID. In *Anais do Workshop de Informática na Escola* (Vol. 23, No. 1, pp. 402-411).
- Fonseca, S., Oliveira, E., Pereira, F., Fernandes, D., & de Carvalho, L. S. G. (2019, November). Adaptação de um método preditivo para inferir o desempenho de alunos de programação. In *Brazilian Symposium on Computers in Education (Simpósio Brasileiro de Informática na Educação-SBIE)* (Vol. 30, No. 1, p. 1651).
- Freitas Júnior, H. B., Pereira, F. D., de Oliveira, E. H. T., de Oliveira, D. B. F., & de Carvalho, L. S. G. (2020, November). Recomendação automática de problemas em juízes online usando processamento de linguagem natural e análise dirigida aos dados. In *Anais do XXXI simpósio brasileiro de informática na educação* (pp. 1152-1161). SBC.
- Google, (2024a). "Blockly". Available in <https://blockly-demo.appspot.com/> (March 2024).
- Google, (2024b). "Blockly factory". Available in <https://developers.google.com/blockly?hl=pt-br> (March 2024).
- Heinen, E. (2015). *Raspiblocos: ambiente de programação didático baseado em Raspberry Pi e Blockly* (Bachelor's thesis, Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná).
- Iturrate, I., Martín, G., García-Zubia, J., Angulo, I., Dziabenko, O., Orduña, P., ... & Fidalgo, A. (2013, October). A mobile robot platform for open learning based on serious games and remote laboratories. In *2013 1st International Conference of the Portuguese Society for Engineering Education (CISPÉE)* (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
- Lima, M., de Carvalho, L. S. G., de Oliveira, E. H. T., Oliveira, D. B. F., & Pereira, F. D. (2020, November). Classificação de dificuldade de questões de programação com base em métricas de código. In *Anais do XXXI Simpósio Brasileiro de Informática na Educação* (pp. 1323-1332). SBC.
- Luxton-Reilly, A., Simon, Albluwi, I., Becker, B. A., Giannakos, M., Kumar, A. N., ... & Szabo, C. (2018, July). Introductory programming: a systematic literature review. In *Proceedings companion of the 23rd annual ACM conference on innovation and technology in computer science education* (pp. 55-106).
- MIT Center for Mobile Learning. "Mit App Inventor". Available in <https://appinventor.mit.edu/> (2024, June).
- Pereira, F. D., Oliveira, E., Cristea, A., Fernandes, D., Silva, L., Aguiar, G., ... & Alshehri, M. (2019). Early dropout prediction for programming courses supported by online judges. In *Artificial Intelligence in Education: 20th International Conference, AIED 2019, Chicago, IL, USA, June 25-29, 2019, Proceedings, Part II 20* (pp. 67-72). Springer International Publishing.
- Ribas, E., Dal Bianco, G., & Lahm, R. A. (2016). Programação visual para introdução ao ensino de programação na Educação Superior: uma análise prática. *RENOTE. Revista Novas Tecnologias na Educação*.
- Saleiro, M., Carmo, B., Rodrigues, J. M., & du Buf, J. H. (2013). A low-cost classroom-oriented educational robotics system. In *Social Robotics: 5th International Conference, ICSR 2013, Bristol, UK, October 27-29, 2013, Proceedings 5* (pp. 74-83). Springer International Publishing.
- Souza, R. P. D. (2018). Uso da biblioteca de programação em blocos Blockly como forma de auxílio ao aprendizado da disciplina de algoritmos e Programação utilizando a linguagem C.
- Sudol, L. A. (2009). *Visual Programming Pedagogies and Integrating Current Visual Programming Language Features*